

SPG Mitteilungen Communications de la SSP

Auszug - Extrait

Physics Anecdotes and Personal Recollections (27)

Optical Metrology

Bernhard Braunecker

This article has been downloaded from:
https://www.sps.ch/articles/physics_anecdotes/

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10115916](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10115916)

Physics Anecdotes and Personal Recollections (27)

Optical Metrology

Bernhard Braunecker

We explain in the following measurement concepts for testing special optical systems. We focus on high resolution imaging lenses as used in airborne photogrammetry and in semiconductor lithography, which need unconventional tools to check image resolution and image distortion.

Airborne Lenses for Photogrammetry

A class of rather unconventional and expensive optical systems were the big cameras for airborne photogrammetry, recording topographic sceneries on high resolution film. These cameras were produced until 2000, then replaced by digital cameras. In their daily use, the cameras were and are exposed to heavy mechanical shocks during take-off and landing of the airplane, to strong vibrations during flight and, above all, to large temperature differences, for example, from +60°C at take-off in the desert to -40°C at an altitude of 3000 m within few minutes. Since the cameras were taken for official surveys, the focal length and the image distortion had to be tested regularly. To this purpose they had to be recalibrated by the lens manufacturer such as Leica Geosystems in Heerbrugg, but also by national authorities as USGS in the USA¹.

Fig. 1: Calibration of a film lens Universal Aviogon UAGS-2 with the electronic vertical goniometer EVG.

After arrival at the factory the focal length and the distortion of the film lenses were measured by an electronic vertical goniometer EVG (Fig. 1), while the optical resolution was visually tested with an official NATO test target by the operators. Then in most cases the lens had to be completely disassembled, all elements cleaned, sometimes some lens surfaces repolished and recoated, and remounted. Thereby the thickness of the mechanical spacers between the lens elements was recalculated and changed by some tenth of μm to correct the focal length and to bring the field distortion and the resolution back to the specification range.

When the film cameras were substituted by digital cameras, we modified the EVG goniometer to a coded vertical go-

Fig. 2: CVG measurement at lens arrival, showing a lens with strong comatic aberrations. Top: Barcode object (red) and its image (blue) with bad contrast values. Bottom: MTF (blue) and PTF (green). Note that the asymmetric code profile, the low MTF values and the non-zero PTF indicate centering errors.

Fig. 3: After correction: Improved MTF values and PTF values nearly to zero. The barcode profile is now symmetric.

niometer CVG. A collimator with a special binary code target simulated the topographic object on ground, and was moved inside the CVG in front of the test lens. The linear codepattern could also be rotated to either point in radial or tangential direction. From all the recorded code images the information about the focal length and the field maps of

¹ <https://www.usgs.gov/>

The relation between both code pattern (red and blue in Fig. 2 and 3) is the optical transfer function OTF, defined as the Fourier transform of the point spread function PSF, that is the impulse response of the optics, i.e. the image of a point source. As Fourier transform, the OTF is complex-valued with a magnitude term called modulation transfer function MTF and a phase transfer function PTF. The PTF is zero if the PSF is symmetric, which is not the case in Fig. 2, but in Fig. 3.

distortion and resolution, both in radial and tangential directions, were obtained.

In Figs. 2 and 3 we see slightly different binary code patterns of contrast one in red and their recorded images by the test lens in blue, which contrast values decrease with higher code frequencies expressed in linepairs/mm. Fig. 2 shows the entrance measurement of a seriously damaged lens after arrival with very low contrast values and asymmetric code bars, indicating internal decentrations. After re-adjusting all lens elements, the MTF contrast values (Fig. 3) were significantly improved, and the code bars were again fully symmetric. In Fig. 4 we see left the CVG and right the spectral and radiometric calibration equipment with a large Ulbricht-sphere, together with the ADS40, the world's first digital airborne photogrammetric camera.

Fig. 4a: Coded vertical goniometer CVG to measure the focal length, the distortion and the OTF of a digital camera ADS40.

Fig. 4b: A large Ulbricht sphere is used for the spectral and radiometric calibration.

Testing Lithographical Systems

Our next example concerns high-performance stepper lenses as those used in chip production. A computer or memory chip consists of many superimposed semiconductor layers, where each layer has a specific current conduction pattern, and all these layers on the chip have to be carefully aligned and interconnected. The layer exposure is a three-step process: first each layer pattern is contact-copied and etched on a glass plate called *template*. Second the template is imaged about ten times smaller on a special glass plate called *reticle*. Then in the third and main step the reticle is used as the object pattern in the wafer factories, where it is imaged by big and very expensive wafer stepper lenses about five to ten times smaller on the semiconductor wafers, now with fabrication and alignment tolerances of some nm.

Reticle Production

In Fig. 5 we illustrate the second step, the reticle production, performed by a combined optical exposure and inspection system. An UV-Excimer laser emitting at 254 nm wavelength is the light source which spatial coherence is reduced by a scrambler to minimize speckle effects on the reticle². Followed by a motorized zoom lens the beam is switched to the exposing path (blue lines) to illuminate the glass template which engraved pattern is imaged about ten times smaller by the reticle imager lens (NA = 0.78) on the glass reticle, coated with photomonomer lacquer. The exposed structures become polymerized by the UV light, and protect the glass material when the reticle is chemically etched outside of the optical system (green box in Fig. 5). The monomer layer of the unexposed area is removed by water rinsing before etching.

Fig. 5: Optical system for reticle exposure (blue path) and reticle inspection (red path)

The new pattern must be inspected for damages as micro-scratches caused by the chemical process. Therefore the developed reticle is re-installed in the optical system, but now the inspection path (red lines) is switched on to illuminate the reticle by a different condenser lens and to image it on a special 2D-UV-sensor. Note that both, the exposure and the inspection arrangements are part of a 'step and go' mechanical system moveable in x and y direction to cover the full reticle area which is much larger than the field of view of the optics.

All the lens optics is made from special UV-glass with high transparency at 254 nm. The imaging lens in our case weighted several kg with very tight optical tolerances, and it was suspended by so-called mechanical flexures. The reason was that the inspection as part of the 'step and go' process required that the imager lens had to be oscillated in resonance by motors along the optical axis with kHz frequency to determine the best image plane. A non-trivial mechanical challenge, since no lateral deflections were allowed.

Due to the permanent mechanical oscillation one had to control regularly the optical performance of the imager lens

² The scrambler is a hexagonal kaleidoscope where by internal reflections the laser point source is seen as extended source of six laser points, but with slightly different phases. This reduces the spatial coherence of the new virtual light source and makes the imaging processes less sensitive to coherent noise (speckle) caused e.g. by micro-scratches in the reticle glass material after chemical etching.

by analyzing so called 'on-axis' aberrations, which are defined as spherical, comatic and astigmatic axial distortions. The first one is caused by tiny dislocations of an optical element along the optical axis, the second one by tilt errors or decentering across the optical axis, and the last one by either rotational errors or by mechanical tensions.

The HPZ³ to detect comatic errors

Decentering or tilting of an optical element across the optical axis is the most likely mechanical defect, and one has to control the centering state of *all* internal lens surfaces. To this purpose a laser beam emitted from a special vario-optics is focused into the center of curvature (CoC) of the front lens surface S_1 of the test lens (Fig. 6). The reflected wavefront from S_1 , which is back focused into its CoC, is imaged by the vario onto a 2D sensor. A surface tilt angle φ_1 of S_1 relative to the optical axis of the test lens and/or the vario leads to an offset position of the laser spot on the sensor. To get rid of the irrelevant coordinate system of the vario, one mounts the test lens on a precise turntable and rotates it. Then the reflected laser spot also rotates on the sensor. Ignoring the circle's centre position and only taking the circle's diameter allows to calculate φ_1 with respect to the turntable axis, which is the best approach of the test lens axis.

As second step one repositions the vario that the laser beam is now reflected from surface S_2 . This is done by focusing the laser beam into the CoC of S_2 , *but as seen through S_1* . Again from the diameter of the reflected laser spot circle on the sensor the tilt angle φ_2 is obtained after correcting the tilt effect of surface S_1 , using its now known tilt angle φ_1 . The process is repeated until the autoreflex of the last lens surface S_N is recorded on the sensor and the last tilt angle φ_N is found with the help of the known tilt angles φ_1 to φ_{N-1} .

Fig. 6: The laser beam is focused by the vario (right) in the centre of curvature CoC of the first surface of the test lens (left). The autoreflex from this surface is imaged on the 2D-sensor. The test lens is rotated to become independent of the coordinate system of the vario.

The result of this kind of 'axial tomographic' iteration is the 3D map of the CoCs of S_1 to S_N . The numerical fit line through them is the best optical axis of the lens with regard to the actual decentrations. The fit weights are determined by optical tolerance calculations⁴. By considering the resid-

ual deviations of the CoCs from the best fit axis, one can decide whether the decentrations are still in tolerance, or individual lens elements must be readjusted, or as worst case the entire objective has to be sent back to the factory.

The AFZ⁵ for automatic lens centering

The HPZ concept was further expanded to increase the efficiency in production, for example for the automatic centering of all lens groups of a geodetic objective. For this purpose, each lens group mounted in a metallic cylindric housing, is clamped in the ball chuck of an automatic lathe. After the 3D position of at least two CoCs had been determined as described before, the ball chuck was adjusted by four servomotors normal to the rotation axis so that the fit axis coincided with the axis of the automatic lathe. Then the metallic cylindric housing was turned with the lathe tool and served as reference cylinder for further installing the lens group into the housing of the objective. The technology was developed by Leica for the automatic centering of triplet lenses for theodolites in large quantities with accuracies in the range of arcseconds.

Coherence Resolved Sensor

Fig. 7 shows the layout of a special interferometer developed by Leica Geosystems in 1997 for ESA^{6,7}. The vario-objective focused the laser beam in the CoCs as described above, however not the CoCs were imaged on the 2D-sensor (CCD), but the surfaces S_1 themselves by installing a Fourier lens in front of the CCD. Then the autoreflected signals from all surfaces were incident as unknown tilted, but plane WF on the sensor and could interfere there with a not tilted, perfect plane WF generated in a reference path by reflection from a perfect mirror. If the optical length in the reference path was adjusted by a movable corner cube to match both path lengths, one received interference fringes on the sensor from which the value of the tilt angle was calculated. The signal discrimination was further significantly improved by using a light source of short coherence length. When testing the method with a lens of same complexity as the lithographic reticle imager of Fig. 6, surface tilt errors could be measured with an accuracy of about 3 arcsec rms.

Fig. 7: Low coherence interferometer

5 Automatisches Flächen Zentriergerät AFZ

6 Design Verification and Failure Diagnosis for Precision Space Optical Systems (DTSO), ESA-Contract No. 11092/94/NL/PB.

7 PCT No. PCT/EP92/02497 Sec. 371 Date Mar. 23, 1994 Sec. 102(e) Date Mar. 23, 1994 PCT Filed Oct.30, 1992 PCT Pub. No. WO93/09395 PCT Pub. Date May 13, 1993.

3 Hoch Präzisions Zentriergerät HPZ

4 Cemented surfaces contribute less strong to the optical quality than glass-air surfaces, so their fit weight is small. Therefore if their autoreflex signal is too weak to be reliably measured, they can be ignored in the iteration in most cases.